

An evaluation of commonly used Kubernetes security scanning tools

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Abstract

With the advent of the edge-cloud continuum, Kubernetes (K8s) has emerged as the prominent solution for service orchestration. In this context, ensuring deployment security is essential. To identify vulnerabilities and misconfigurations in a timely and efficient manner, security scanning tools are employed. In this work, we evaluate six widely used security tools for workload and static code analysis. We consider several factors, including scan time, the number of detected threats, and resource usage. This evaluation seeks not only to demonstrate the performance trade-offs of these tools but also to contribute additional insights into their practical capabilities.

CCS Concepts

• Networks → Cloud computing; • Security and privacy → Network security.

Keywords

Kubernetes, Security, Risk Analysis, Edge-cloud Continuum

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the edge-cloud continuum has transformed the way modern microservice-based applications are designed, deployed, and managed. This continuum relies heavily on meta-operating systems (metaOSs) [8, 27] which essentially abstract the underlying infrastructure to enable the seamless integration [26], AI-driven workload management [19] and meta-orchestration [14] of heterogeneous edge and cloud resources. By coupling this abstraction layer with AI capabilities, metaOSs have led to the introduction of Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) frameworks [12, 20], which leverage AI for optimal task scheduling and deployment across the cloud-fog-edge continuum.

Kubernetes (K8s) has become a key enabler in realizing the metaOS -and ultimately the computing continuum- vision and has evolved as the defacto solution for service orchestration. Considering the ever-growing adoption of K8s, its security emerges as

an aspect of major importance. As a matter of fact, the 'State of Kubernetes Security Report' for 2024, provided by Red Hat [15], revealed that 42% of 600 professionals-respondents, identify security as a top concern in container and Kubernetes strategies. Improperly configured or unsecured Kubernetes clusters can expose applications and infrastructure to severe security issues, including unauthorized access, data breaches, and privilege escalation. The aforementioned survey showed also that 46% of organizations lost revenue or customers due to a container or Kubernetes security incident. Therefore, the importance of securing K8s deployments is indisputable and necessitates specialized mechanisms to ensure that best practices are in place.

To address these concerns, many tools have been developed to perform security risk analysis in K8s deployments, throughout the entire development lifecycle. Such tools are designed to detect potential cluster vulnerabilities and/or misconfigurations. On the one hand, vulnerability detection pertains to discovering weaknesses, e.g. in container images or runtime environments, that are potentially exploitable by attackers. Misconfiguration detection, on the other hand, aims at identifying poor configurations, such as overly permissive role-based access control (RBAC) policies, that can increase the attack surface of a K8s cluster.

Nevertheless, K8s security remains a rather underexplored area, while lacking a pragmatic evaluation of K8s security tools. This paper aims to evaluate and compare the performance of Kubernetes security scanning tools in the presence of a honeypot that exposes several security risks. For this purpose, we set up a dedicated K8s cluster to serve as a controlled environment for testing these tools and we utilize Kubernetes Goat [1] to render our cluster intentionally vulnerable. Kubernetes Goat simulates common k8s misconfigurations and security vulnerabilities, enabling a realistic assessment of each tool's capability to detect risks and provide remediation methods.

We are benchmarking a set of six widely used Kubernetes security tools, including both workload scanners (namely Trivy [5] and Kubescape [6]) and static code analysis tools (i.e., KubeLint [24], Terrascan [25], Checkov [9] and Kubesec [11]). In this effort, we consider both command-line interface (CLI) and k8s operator tools. The performance of these tools is assessed with respect to scan time and detection accuracy, while the operators are further evaluated in terms of resource usage, including CPU, memory, and bandwidth consumption.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that evaluates K8s security scanning tools, thus offering empirical results on their actual vulnerability and misconfiguration detection capabilities. In summary, our work demonstrates that static analysis tools identify any misconfigurations in the pre-deployment phase, while workload scanning tools offer more thorough security assessments at

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runtime, typically with increased, but not prohibitive, scan times and resource usage. This highlights the importance of leveraging both static analyzers and workload scanners to ensure robust security along the deployment lifecycle. Overall, our study aims to provide practical insights that can be quite useful for Kubernetes security and DevSecOps practitioners.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section 2 we overview related works. Section 3 presents the considered K8s security scanning tools. In Section 4 we delineate the evaluation setup and methodology per tool, while Section 5 presents the evaluation results. Finally, Section 6 discusses the key findings of our study and Section 7 summarizes our conclusions.

2 Related Work

The increasing importance of K8s security has prompted several studies addressing this topic. However, most prior research primarily discusses and categorizes tools and practices for securing K8s deployments, rather than providing practical results.

One notable work is a grey literature review of K8s security practices conducted by practitioners, as reported in [23]. This review derived a list of eleven commonly used K8s security practices. Among these, vulnerability scanning emerged as one of the most widely adopted methods for enhancing K8s security.

Another area of interest is the security misconfigurations found in K8s manifests, which is explored in the empirical study [22]. This study proposes a taxonomy that includes eleven categories of security misconfigurations. Based on their evaluation, the authors identified 1,051 instances affecting 13.9% of 4,707 Kubernetes objects, demonstrating that security misconfigurations in K8s manifests are quite common. In a similar vein, [17] reviews existing K8s security vulnerabilities and relevant mitigation strategies.

A few works focus on more pragmatic evaluations. For instance, [13] compared three generic honeypots—ContainerSSH, Cowrie, and sshesame—on the Compliant Kubernetes (CK8s) platform. While this study evaluated honeypots for container environments, the solutions examined were not specifically designed for K8s. Furthermore, [28] assessed the security-performance trade-offs in alternative Kubernetes container runtimes, specifically Kata and gVisor. The authors experimented with three benchmark applications, demonstrating that enhanced security often incurs significant costs in deployment time, application performance, and memory usage, although CPU overhead might remain relatively minor. While their focus differs from ours, this study emphasizes the need for balance between security and performance in Kubernetes environments.

The authors of [16] developed kube-security-scanner, a custom benchmarking tool that is built upon the open-source security scanners Kubescape, Trivy, kube-score, and kube-bench. This tool evaluates the security posture of various K8s environments, including k3s, RKE2, Amazon's EKS, and Google Kubernetes Engine (GKE). The scans performed with their tool revealed that k3s exhibited the fewest overall weaknesses in terms of resource misconfigurations and container image vulnerabilities.

Lastly, the work presented in [7] is the one most closely related to ours. This study focuses on Container Network Interface (CNI) plugins that provide security assurances through network policies. It compares Calico and Cilium in terms of latency and throughput

in inter- and intra-node scenarios, finding that Calico outperforms Cilium, particularly in inter-node scenarios. Further evaluation of Calico demonstrated negligible performance impact when increasing the number of policies, varying policy recipes, or scaling the number of pods matching the policy criteria. In addition, the authors discuss the security implications and vulnerabilities associated with network policies for inter-container communication.

Overall, it becomes evident that the current literature lacks research works that provide practical insights into K8s security mechanisms. Our paper aims to fill this gap by evaluating several CLI tools and operator-based solutions based on scan time and their ability to identify risks. It further contributes to the state-of-the-art by demonstrating how these tools perform under realistic security threat conditions in a honeypot-enabled purposely vulnerable environment.

3 Kubernetes Security Scanning Tools

In this work, we compare six well-known K8s security scanning tools that are designed to detect configuration issues and security vulnerabilities, namely:

- Trivy (CLI and operator)
- Kubescape (CLI and operator)
- KubeLinter (CLI)
- Terrascan (CLI)
- Checkov (CLI)
- Kubesecc (CLI)

The selected tools were determined like so: Firstly, we focused on open-source solutions. Secondly, considering their popularity among professionals, which was assessed based on the findings of Red Hat's 'State of Kubernetes Security Report' for 2024 [15]. In that regard, we specifically opted for scanning tools and left out the tools designed for other purposes, such as the Open Policy Agent Gatekeeper [10] for policy enforcement. Lastly, we also included Kubescape and Kubesecc, two tools widely adopted by the K8s community.

We hereafter provide a brief qualitative comparison of the considered solutions.

Trivy [5], maintained by Aqua Security, presents itself as an all-in-one security scanning solution. It incorporates several features and functionalities that were previously provided separately by kube-bench and kube-hunter. For instance, testing the compliance with the CIS Kubernetes Benchmark. Especially kube-hunter is no longer under active development and its maintainers propose shifting to Trivy instead. Therefore, although both kube-bench and kube-hunter were two of the top candidates in Red Hat's report, we chose to experiment with Trivy instead.

Trivy performs a variety of security scans, including scanning the entire cluster for vulnerabilities, misconfigurations, exposed secrets, and others or checking specific manifest files for misconfigurations and vulnerabilities. In the former case, in-cluster security scans are automatically triggered every time the state of the cluster changes. In manifest scanning, besides its default mechanisms, Trivy also supports Open Policy Agent (OPA) to enable scanning through custom policies. The generated scan logs are summarised in security reports available as Kubernetes Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) and accessible through the Kubernetes API.

It can be deployed either as a CLI or as a Kubernetes Operator inside a cluster.

Kubescape [6] by ARMO is an open-source security tool that performs security assessments against known security benchmarks, such as the NSA-CISA Kubernetes Hardening Guide, the MITRE ATT&CK framework, and the CIS Benchmark. It supports both runtime cluster scans and pre-deployment checks, to identify potential risks and vulnerabilities in Kubernetes workloads, configurations, and infrastructure. Overall, Kubescape is a valuable tool for ensuring cluster adherence to best practices and security guidelines. It can also be used at any stage of CI/CD pipelines, being a great addition to DevSecOps practices.

It can be deployed either as a CLI or as a Kubernetes Operator inside a cluster.

KubeLinter [24] by StackRox, is designed to run checks on specific Kubernetes YAML files or directories containing the YAML manifests. It does not perform generic checks on active Kubernetes clusters or without specifying input files. Instead, its primary functionality is to analyze Kubernetes configuration files (YAML or Helm charts) for misconfigurations before deployment to ensure that they follow security and operational best practices. For each lint error found during the scan, it proposes a remediation method.

Terrascan [25], developed by tenable, is a static code analyzer for Infrastructure as Code (IaC) designed for detecting compliance and security violations. It provides a wide variety of out-of-the-box policies to enable IaC scanning against common policy standards such as the CIS Benchmark. It also supports OPA to allow for extending its codebase with custom policies.

Checkov [9], maintained by Prisma Cloud, is also an IaC static code analysis tool that finds security and compliance misconfigurations through graph-based scanning. It can be seamlessly integrated into DevSecOps processes as a part of the CI/CD pipelines. Checkov generates detailed reports on scanning results, highlighting any identified policy violations and suggesting remediation steps.

Kubesecc [11], provided by controlplane, is another static analysis tool. It analyzes the security risks of K8s resources by checking the configuration and manifests files to identify any vulnerabilities. For every vulnerability found, it provides a so-called severity score, which indicates its criticality.

4 Evaluation Setup

For our evaluation, we have set up a dedicated K8s cluster, consisting of one master and two worker nodes. The nodes are running Kubernetes v1.32.0. Each node is a virtual machine (VM) running Ubuntu 24.04.1. In terms of hardware, each node has 4vCPUs and 20GB disk. The master node has a memory of 16GB, while each worker node has 4GB memory.

Our experimental environment is as follows: We have used vCluster 0.21.2 [18] to create an isolated, virtual cluster on top of the host cluster, wherein the honeypot is running. In other words, only the virtual cluster was rendered intentionally vulnerable. That way, a certain level of abstraction was achieved to ensure that the vulnerable resources running within the virtual cluster don't directly affect the host cluster's state, whereas the physical resources are shared.

In this virtual cluster, we employed the Kubernetes Goat honeypot v2.3.0 [1], that exposes K8s vulnerabilities and misconfigurations, offering a wide range of scenarios such as K8s namespaces bypass, exploiting exposed NodePort and private registries.

For each tool, we measure the scan time and number of threats detected. Lastly, the operators are running as pods within their respective namespace. Therefore, only for the solutions that are available as K8s operators (i.e., Trivy and Kubescape), it was feasible to monitor the resource usage, as well. To achieve so, we have used kube-prometheus v0.14.0 [21] to measure CPU, memory and bandwidth usage upon scans.

4.1 Tools utility & scan capabilities

As presented in Section 3, our evaluation involves both workload scanners (Trivy and Kubescape) and static manifests analysis tools (KubeLinter, Terrascan, Checkov, Kubesecc).

The scans were performed based on the capabilities and utility of each tool, as outlined below:

- **Trivy**
 - Operator: To initiate a new scan, we removed any previously generated vulnerability or misconfiguration reports. After deletion, a new scan was automatically triggered. The Trivy-operator creates dedicated jobs for scanning.
 - CLI: Command-based scanning of the virtual cluster.
- **Kubescape**
 - Operator: Supports command-based scanning of specific workloads. Consequently, we performed scans on every honeypot pod operating within the virtual cluster.
 - CLI: Similarly to the operator, we scanned each honeypot pod running in the virtual cluster.
- **KubeLinter, Checkov, and Kubesecc**: These tools allowed linting of the honeypot directory that contained the misconfigured manifest files.
- **Terrascan and Kubesecc**: These tools are used to scan and validate specific manifest files. To streamline this process, a bash script was developed to automate the scanning of all manifests provided by the honeypot.

It is important to note that in the case of the operators, when one is running, the other is deactivated to ensure that they operate independently within the same setup. For example, when the Kubescape operator was active, the Trivy deployment was scaled down to zero replicas.

5 Results

5.1 Scan time

We first evaluate the tools in terms of the time needed for the respective scans to be completed. Scan time results are averaged over 5 runs, to ensure results accuracy. Associated results for the workload scanners are presented in Table 1 and for the static analysis tools in Table 2.

First, based on the results, we conclude that workload scanning is more time-consuming than static code analysis. This is expected, as scanning an actual deployment involves more thorough inspections and checks than validating configuration files, which typically occurs during the pre-deployment phase.

Workload scanner	Scan Type	Scan Time (seconds)
Trivy	Operator-based vulnerability scanning	132
	Operator-based misconfigurations scanning	4
	CLI-based cluster scanning	96
Kubescape	Operator-based vulnerability scanning	8
	Operator-based misconfigurations scanning	47
	CLI-based workload scanning	274

Table 1: Time taken for scanning per workload scanner

Static Analysis Tool	Scan Time (seconds)
KubeLinter	0.086
Terrascan	15.4
Checkov	3.5
Kubesecc	11.4

Table 2: Time taken for scanning per static analysis tool

Focusing on operator-based workload scanning, Kubescape appears to be faster than Trivy for vulnerability scanning. The reason for this may be the additional delays introduced by Trivy. More specifically, on the one hand, the Trivy operator creates dedicated jobs for scanning, which adds delays due to the time needed for new pod creation and scheduling. Moreover, by default, each pod created by a scan job downloads the Trivy vulnerabilities database from the GitHub releases page and stores it in the local file system [4]. On the other hand, Trivy stores the generated reports as custom CRDs, further contributing to the overall scan time.

In contrast, when it comes to misconfiguration detection, the Trivy operator outperforms significantly the Kubescape operator. The same applies to the CLIs, wherein the Trivy CLI needs about one-third of the time required by the Kubescape operator.

Interestingly, the time taken by the Trivy operator for detecting misconfigurations is comparable to, and in some cases even less than, the time required by certain static analysis tools. Among these tools, Terrascan takes the longest to complete scanning tasks, while KubeLinter stands out as the fastest scanner.

5.2 Threat detection

In this subsection, we compare the threat detection results acquired by each CLI tool for a certain scenario provided by Kubernetes Goat, namely the Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF) attack in the Kubernetes world. SSRF is the go-to attack vector for cloud-native environments wherein the attacker exploits K8s-native features such as service discovery and service DNS queries to gain access to internal microservices [2].

Results are listed in Table 3. For Trivy and Kubescape, the count of detected threats declares the total vulnerabilities and misconfigurations. For KubeLinter and Kubesecc the measured threats correspond to lint errors, while for Terrascan and for Checkov they reflect the number of violated policies and failed tests, respectively.

Trivy and Kubescape, exhibiting 1202 and 1261 threat detections respectively, show a high detection ratio. The similarity in

	Tool	Detected Threats
Workload scanners	Trivy	1202
	Kubescape	1261
Static analysis tools	KubeLinter	8
	Terrascan	41
	Checkov	35
	Kubesecc	2

Table 3: Number of threat detections per tool

their detection counts suggests that both tools offer wide coverage, although their testing criteria might differ slightly.

Static analysis tools identify fewer threats compared to workload scanners. This is expected since they analyze the deployment code for misconfigurations and policy violations rather than assessing the security posture of actively running workloads.

These tools aim to identify Kubernetes configuration issues, such as missing resource limits or exploitable configurations. The lower number of detections might stem from a more restricted set of rules, policies, or configurations being analyzed, depending on the tool, with Kubesecc appearing to have the narrowest detection scope.

Overall, tools like Terrascan and Checkov excel in IaC analysis, while Trivy and Kubescape are more suitable for detecting runtime workload issues. This indicates that using such kind of tools at different deployment steps can prove to be very beneficial for achieving comprehensive security visibility.

5.3 Resource usage

As already mentioned, measuring resource usage was feasible only for operators, as they run as pods that can be monitored. Consequently, this subsection focuses on the two operators, Trivy and Kubescape.

The results shown in Figures 1 and 2, illustrate the CPU, memory and network usage as monitored by Prometheus during the scans. The scans lasted for 5 minutes in total, as shown in the Figures'

x-axes. In this period, we first perform a vulnerability scanning (taking place in the first 2 minutes) and subsequently, a misconfigurations scanning (happening in the last 3 minutes). This allows for capturing the performance per scan type more accurately.

This is especially useful in the case of the Kubescape operator which uses two different components, namely kubevuln and kubescape, which are responsible for vulnerability and misconfiguration scanning, respectively. In addition, a separate pod, called storage, manages the storing of the scan results.

Comparing the resource consumption of the operator-based scan tools indicates that the CPU usage is nearly equal in both cases. It also becomes evident that misconfiguration scanning is more CPU-intensive compared to vulnerability scanning as shown by the increase in CPU usage during the last 3 minutes in Figures 1a and 2a. That can be because misconfiguration scanning involves parsing and validating YAML manifests against a large set of policies and rules, which adds computational overhead.

When zooming into the Kubescape operator (Figure 2a), this observation is in line with the scan time results presented in section 5.1, which showed that misconfiguration scanning is much slower than vulnerability scanning. In the case of the Trivy operator, although misconfiguration scanning is faster than vulnerability scanning, it appears to be more CPU-intensive. This can be explained by the fact that vulnerability scanning is performed by dedicated scan jobs/pods, each of which consumes a certain amount of resources. Since the operator itself is only responsible for managing these jobs—rather than executing the scans—it has relatively low CPU usage. In contrast, for misconfiguration scanning, the operator is the one installing the configuration audit policies and performing policies validation [3], hence resulting in higher CPU consumption.

In terms of memory consumption, Trivy utilizes slightly more memory than Kubescape, peaking at 2%, as opposed to Kubescape that reaches a maximum of 0.9% (Figures 1b and 2b). This can be justified by the fact that reports are stored as new CRDs.

Moreover, the Kubescape operator requires a certain amount of network bandwidth to facilitate internal communication among its subcomponents (Figure 2c), particularly for populating and storing the scan results. On the contrary, Trivy operates without such inter-component communication overhead, and as such, it does not occupy any network resources (Figure 1c).

Despite these differences, both operators exhibit overall low resource usage, making them well-suited for environments with limited resources, such as edge networks.

6 Key Takeaways & Discussion

The comparative analysis of static code analysis tools and workload scanning tools conducted in our study demonstrates their respective strengths and trade-offs, offering valuable insights into their practical applications.

Static analysis tools like KubeLint, Terrascan, Checkov and Kubesec specialize in detecting misconfigurations and policy violations with minimal latency by linting K8s manifest files, making them particularly useful in the pre-deployment phase.

In contrast, workload scanning tools like Trivy and Kubescape provide runtime threat detection by assessing the security posture of actual deployments. However, this comes at the cost of

higher scan times and resource usage. The Trivy operator, while slightly slower than Kubescape in vulnerability detection, performs exceptionally well in detecting misconfigurations, competing and sometimes even outperforming static analysis tools in speed.

Each operator follows a distinct approach with its pros and cons: Kubescape delegates tasks such as vulnerability scanning to dedicated subcomponents, introducing complexity and network overhead, whereas Trivy creates separate scan jobs/pods and stores reports as CRDs, leading to slightly higher memory consumption. Nonetheless, both operators maintain low overall resource footprints, advocating their suitability for resource-constrained environments, such as edge networks.

The findings indicate that static and workload scanning tools can be complementary. Static analysis tools offer an efficient and lightweight approach to identify configuration and policy issues early in the development lifecycle, while workload scanners detect critical runtime vulnerabilities and misconfigurations of deployments. Therefore, to enhance security issues' visibility and posture, employing static analysis tools during the pre-deployment stage and workload scanners post-deployment can ensure comprehensive coverage throughout the entire deployment workflow.

7 Conclusions

In this paper, we evaluated six commonly used Kubernetes (K8s) security tools for scanning vulnerabilities and misconfigurations: Trivy, Kubescape, KubeLint, Terrascan, Checkov, and Kubesec. We compared these tools based on their scan time and the number of threats detected. For the two solutions available as operators—Trivy and Kubescape—we also measured their CPU, memory, and network bandwidth usage.

Our findings indicate that both operators are generally resource-efficient, particularly regarding CPU consumption. However, Trivy tends to have higher memory requirements, while Kubescape requires more network resources. Overall, to achieve optimal visibility of security threats, static analysis tools offer lightweight and fast solutions during the pre-deployment phase, whereas active workload scanners are more effective for risk assessments during deployment.

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Figure 1: Resource usage for Trivy Operator

Figure 2: Resource Usage for Kubescape Operator

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